

STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF CEMENT-CONCRETE MODIFIED WITH BINARY MICROPRODUCER

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Annotation. This article presents the results of studies on the water requirements of the binder of ash spark and limestone-based binary additives to the composition of cement, the duration of hardening, the separation of water, the penetration in the process of hardening cement stone, its strength and other similar properties.

Key words: Limestone, binary additives, concrete, ash spark, strength, deformation at the entrance.

Introduction. At the current stage of the development of the world construction industry, the production of materials that are an alternative to traditional construction materials based on the processing of large tonnage of industrial waste using innovative low-energy and environmentally friendly technologies is a priority [1].

Work on the design of modified concrete composition, development of practical recommendations on physical-mechanical and chemical properties using large amounts of industrial waste generated in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan is being intensively carried out. One of the important issues in the implementation of these tasks is the creation and improvement of existing technologies for the production of extremely high-quality and long-lasting constructions and products using binary microfillers of various natures based on the "quartz + carbonate" system [2].

In the cement industry, the production of composite binders as an alternative to the main binder with low energy consumption is a promising direction, because it is not only related to reducing energy consumption and reducing CO₂ gas emissions into the atmosphere, but also to obtaining cement composites with a set of different functional properties. In the building materials industry, it should be highlighted that the concept of "green concrete, ecological concrete" has been developed, which combines the actual issues of modernization of construction to use industrial waste to save Portland cement clinker and obtain concrete with improved properties, and in this, a great emphasis is placed on the use of binary microaggregates [3].

In this article, the construction and technical properties of cement stone modified with the help of binary microfillers are studied.

Purpose and methods of research. In the research, ЦЕМИ 32.5 N Portlandcement from the "Ohangarontsement" plant was used for the preparation of heavy concrete, new Angren TPP fly ash and limestone from the Muruntov mine were used as carbonate rock to obtain a complex microfiller (chemical composition is given in table 1).

Table 1

Chemical composition of the ash spark of the new Angren TPP

Type of microfiller	The composition of oxides, mas. %											
	S	A	F	C	M	M	N	K	S	T	P	n
New Angren TPP ash spark	4	1	1	1	3	-	0	1	1	0	-	1

The mineral composition of the carbonate rock is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Mineral composition of carbonate rock

Mineralogical composition (%)	Limestone (Muruntov)
Calcite	98
Quartz	2
Muscovite	-
Montmorillonite	-
Dolomite	-

Cement stone samples were prepared from cement paste of normal density. The normal density and setting time of cement paste are determined on the VIKA device in accordance with GOST 310.3-76.

The strength of cement stone was determined at the age of 28 days in 2x2x2 cm samples stored at a temperature of 20±2°C with 95-100 % humidity.

Determination of the water separation of the ingredients was carried out in accordance with GOST310.6-2020.

Deformations in penetration and creep were determined in accordance with GOST 24544-81.

Results and their discussion. It is known that the type of mineral microfiller, its dosage, the chemical and mineralogical composition of raw materials, and their dispersion have a significant effect on the processes of forming the structure of cement stone [5, 6].

The optimal composition of portland cement with complex microfillers was developed based on the experimental plan and in accordance with [7-9] the contents of the study are presented in table 3.

Table 3

Researched compositions and their strength indicators

№	Compound composition, %			Strength, MPa	
	Portland cement, TsEMI 32,5 H	A spark ash	Lime stone S _{SS} =3 000 sm ² /g	R ⁷ _{com} , MPa	R ²⁸ _{com} , MPa
1 (benchmark content)	100	-	-	37,2	48,3
2	95	5	-	32,4	51,2
3	80	15	5	28,2	50,2

4	90	5	5	38,2	52,6
5	75	10	15	37,1	49,3
6	95	-	5	39,7	53,4
7	80	10	10	36,5	47,8
8	75	15	10	33,1	47,1
9	80	-	20	37,4	48,2
10	90	-	10	34,9	45,6
11	85	-	15	37,7	48,0
12	85	15	-	32,3	50,6
13	80	20	-	31,4	49,8
14	75	25	-	29,3	48,4
15	75	5	20	31,8	44,7

Partial replacement of portland cement paste with fly ash and limestone compared some compositions with the reference composition (Contents №2-6 %; 3-3 %; №4-8 %; №6-10.5 %; №12-3.5 %; №13-1.5 %) led to an increase in durability indicators. It should also be noted that in the compositions with added ash spark. At the age of 7 days, there was a decrease in strength compared to the standard, and then an increase in strength properties was observed when the hardening period was 28 days. (Contents №3; №12; №13; №14). In our opinion, this is due to the pussol reaction that occurs during hydration.

From the point of view of the minimum consumption of cement and the proportional strength compared to the standard composition, compositions №5 and №14 are considered optimal compositions. Based on this point of view, content №1; №5 and №14 were used in further studies to determine the physico-mechanical and physico-chemical properties.

The water requirement of Portland cement is estimated by the amount of water required to obtain a cement paste. The normal density of cement paste is defined as the consistency that provides mobility and convenient placement, as well as the possibility of densely filling the mold. From the results presented in Table 4, it can be seen that the normal density of Portland cement with the addition of fly ash increased by 2 points compared to the standard composition. In the case of carbonate cement, this indicator is 25 %. It follows that the information presented in the analysis of the literature was confirmed, that is, limestone cement reduces the water requirement of the binder. In composition №3 with binary additive, the normal density is 1 point lower than the index of cement binder. The use of limestone in composition №3 reduces the adverse effect of power spark on water demand.

Table 4

Contents	Normal thickness, %	Hardening time, min	
		Start, min	End, min
Portland cement	27	70	380
Portland cement (PCH) (75 %)+ a spark of ash (SA) (25 %)	30	80	410
Portland cement (75 %)+ SA (10 %)+ limestone powder (LP) (15 %)	27	80	450

In a series of studies on the use of carbonate rocks in the composition of Portland cement [10-12], the ability of using limestone to slow down the hardening rate of cement paste was noted. The results obtained for determining the setting time of the cement binder with binary microfiller content given in table 4 are consistent with the opinion of these authors.

Water separation is observed during laboratory tests, as well as during the production of concrete mixture on construction sites. During the hardening process, some cements retain water in the mixture, while others release some of it. The released water covers the upper surface of the samples in the form of a layer of different thickness or flows through the gaps between the mold and the base.

As the amount of water required for mixing decreases, the water separation property of cements also decreases. However, when determining the setting time of cement paste, even when the ratio of water and cement is very small ($W/S=0.27$) a significant separation of water can be noticed in a number of binders. This phenomenon is more evident in concrete. Separation of water in the mixture is of great importance to obtain concrete with a homogeneous structure and to ensure reliable bonding of cement with filler and steel reinforcement. The leaching water collects on the successive layers of concrete, which interferes with the cohesion of the layers and leads to the formation of a weak layer between them with a relatively high water content. This layering of concrete destroys the structural integrity of monolithic concrete and ultimately reduces its strength. Layering occurs not only on the surface of laid concrete layers, but also inside it, between cement + fillers. Separated water within the concrete mixture usually accumulates under the subsurface of the larger aggregates and reinforcements, which causes the cement stone to weaken its bond with the aggregates and reinforcements. In addition, when the separated water evaporates, large pores are formed, facilitating the filtration of water into the concrete. At present, a draft standard [12] has been developed, which specifies that the separation of water from the concrete mix should not exceed 31 % in the production of road and airfield pavements and reinforced concrete products and bridge structures.

The separation of water from Portland cement largely depends on the mineralogical and granulometric composition of the clinker, as well as the relative surface area. The separation of water decreases with the increase of the aluminate phases in the clinker and the relative surface area of the cement. Mineral additives included in the composition of Portland cement have different effects on the water separation properties of cement. Studies have shown that the use of fly ash, microkermensium, barkhan sand, etc. increases the water release from the mixture, and mineral additives such as limestone, trepel, diatomite reduce the water release from the cement paste [13].

Composite cement compositions with binary microfillers were prepared using cement based on "Ohangarontsement" JSC cement clinker to study the water separation properties of the investigated compositions (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. of the researched content (reference content 1; 2-PTs 75 % + SA 25 %; 3-PTs 75 % + SA 10 % + LP 15 %) dependence on the water separation coefficient

As can be seen from the above results, the addition of 25 % fly ash to the cement resulted in a significant increase in the water separation coefficient of 14 % compared to the cement without addition. Replacing part of the slag with limestone powder provided a reduction of this indicator by 7 % compared to the reference content.

According to the analyzed property, composite portland cement with binary addition (composition №3) can be considered optimal. The beneficial effect of carbonate additives on reducing the water release of composite cement is, in our opinion, due to the increase in hydration products that are in a colloidal state during the initial period of setting and have the ability to hold water.

During the solidification of cement stone, volumetric changes occur, which in scientific literature is called shrinkage (shrinkage) and leads to a decrease in the size of the products. Penetration, a deformation property, is one of the key properties of concrete quality and requires optimization along with properties such as strength and corrosion resistance.

The amount of penetration deformation depends on the mineralogical and chemical composition of the binder, relative surface area, water-cement ratio, additives in the cement and other factors. With the increase of water-cement ratio and cement dispersion, the penetration deformation during hardening increases significantly.

Penetration of cement stone is usually 3-4 mm/m, in cement mixes - 0.6-1.4 mm/m, in heavy concrete - 0.3-0.5 mm/m. The main part of insertion deformations occurs during the first 3-4 months of hardening [13].

A study of shrinkage deformations of the investigated compositions during solidification was carried out (Fig. 6). Researches were conducted on samples of 4x4x16 cm size, made of cement paste of normal well size and stored under normal conditions.

As can be seen from the graph above, the inclusion of fly ash and limestone powder in the cement composition contributes to a significant reduction of the initial deformation of the binder during the hardening process. A 28-day period was observed to reduce the initial deformation of the complex microfiller composition consisting of 10 % SA and 15% carbonate rock-based powder stored under normal conditions compared to the control composition and by 25 % compared to composition 2.

A reduction in the penetration deformations of cement can lead to a decrease in the level of local stresses in the concrete matrix, which is considered the main cause of crack formation.

Figure 6. Of the researched compositions (1st reference composition; 2nd PTs 75 % + SA 25 %; 3-PTs 75 % + SA 10 % + LP 15 %) deformations during shrinkage

It is very important to use Portland cements with a low shrinkage index in restoration and repair works, as well as in the construction of buildings and structures by the integral casting method.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be noted that the use of binary microfiller improves the strength, water separation and linear deformation properties of the cement binder.

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